

Portable Intrusion Detection in IoT Enabled Smart City Networks: A Comparative Study of Machine Learning Models

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Abstract—The Internet of Things (IoT) is transforming many industries through the integration of the Internet with electronic and mechanical devices, as well as sensors, to make more intelligent systems in applications such as healthcare, smart homes, and public safety. This rapid growth in IoT devices has resulted in significant security risks, turning these systems into targets for cybercriminals. To counter these weaknesses, Network Intrusion Detection Systems are deployed, which monitor network traffic to identify potential malicious activities. This paper evaluates the performance of machine learning models in detecting intrusions within IoT-enabled smart city networks. For this, the UNSW-NB15 dataset is used, which contains realistic network traffic. The dataset was preprocessed, including handling missing data, one-hot encoding categorical variables, and normalizing numerical features. The paper performs multi-class classification to identify specific attack types. We tested various machine learning algorithms, including Decision Tree, K-Nearest Neighbor, Linear Regression, etc. classifiers. The preprocessed dataset contained 61 attributes with 81,173 entries, which was sufficient for the models to be thoroughly tested. The results provide a lot of insight into the strengths and weaknesses of various machine learning techniques in improving the security of IoT networks, especially in critical applications in smart cities.

Index Terms—internet of things, machine learning, security risks, smart cities

I. INTRODUCTION

Rapid advancements in the Internet of Things have really transformed enterprises through the enabling of extraordinary connectivity and automation across various industries. The Internet of Things has enabled intelligent solutions for various key sectors, including healthcare, smart homes, transportation, and public safety—all due to a vast number of integrated devices, sensors, and systems. Statistics projects that the number of IoT devices will surge beyond 29 billion by 2030, representing extensive adoptions of this disruptive technology. In parallel with exponential expansion comes considerable security vulnerability, resulting in very severe threats to individuals and businesses alike. To date, with increasing deployment, IoT devices have progressively become targets of hackers by exploiting such well-known vulnerabilities as using default

or hardwired passwords, insecure network configurations, and poor security protocols.

A large portion of enterprises poorly secure their IoT infrastructure, leaving systems vulnerable to attacks that could lead to data breaches, operational disruptions, and even physical harm. The likes of the Mirai botnet attack have demonstrated how hacked IoT devices can be used to carry out large-scale Distributed Denial-of-Service attacks, underscoring the need for improvements in IoT security. Given all these issues, NIDS plays an important role in the monitoring of network traffic, detecting malicious actions within an IoT ecosystem. This work involves an analysis of the different machine learning models for the detection of intrusion in the IoT-integrated smart city networks.

This paper presents the evaluation of different machine learning algorithms using the UNSW-NB15 dataset, which includes a complete set of real network traffic data for finding the best performance regarding detection and classification of anomalous traffic or particular attack types. This research introduces a new application for remote network intrusion detection. It uses machine learning algorithms to analyze network data in real time, allowing users to monitor and fix security issues from any location proactively. The study aims at enhancing IoT security in smart city environments by integrating thorough data analysis with user-friendly and practical solutions, thus contributing to safer and more robust systems for vital infrastructure and users.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Machine learning techniques have been extensively applied to enhance the performance of intrusion detection systems. For instance, Geyer and Carle [1] proposed a method that combines ML with automated protocol design to improve network management and security. Their approach utilizes supervised and unsupervised learning techniques to optimize routing protocols based on real-time network conditions, thereby enhancing the resilience of smart city networks against intrusions. IoT based applications have increased rapidly in recent years.

Some of the recent works are mentioned here as well to signify the importance of network intrusion. For example, the integration of automated attendance management systems has transformed traditional methods of tracking attendance in educational and organizational settings [2]. A systematic literature review in 2022 highlights the effectiveness of various technologies [3]. Other works include food delivery robots [4], [5], IoT heart monitoring systems [6], computer vision monitoring [7] etc. Application-aware protocols play a critical role in optimizing network resources based on specific application requirements. Research by Guha Roy et al. [8] discusses how application-layer protocols like MQTT-SN can be enhanced through ML techniques to estimate end-to-end delays and message loss effectively. This adaptation not only improves communication efficiency but also strengthens the overall security posture by ensuring that critical applications receive the necessary resources to function securely under varying network conditions. Moreover, Kumar et al. [9] highlighted the significance of vulnerability mining using ML models in IoT network protocols. The study emphasizes how ML can identify potential vulnerabilities by analyzing abnormal data patterns, which is crucial for preemptively addressing security threats in IoT environments [8]. This proactive approach is essential in smart cities where the interconnectedness of devices can amplify the impact of security breaches. Despite the advancements in ML-based IDS, several challenges remain. The high computational demands of some ML algorithms can lead to increased latency, which is detrimental in real-time applications typical in smart cities. Furthermore, the need for extensive labeled datasets for training poses a significant hurdle, as acquiring such data can be resource-intensive and time-consuming [10].

Elif et al. [11] devised a semi-supervised anomaly detection system employing the k-means algorithm to detect network assaults. During training, normal samples were grouped, and a threshold was determined based on distances from cluster centroids utilizing a validation dataset. Evaluation on the NSL-KDD dataset confirmed the method's efficacy, attaining an accuracy of above 80%. A framework for intrusion detection was suggested using swarm optimization with parameter tuning and feature selection in multiple criteria linear programming (MCLP) and support vector machine (SVM) [12]. The approach enhances detection and reduces false alarm rates by limiting characteristics, utilizing chaotic principles and adaptive parameters to improve efficiency. Experiments on the NSL-KDD dataset exhibited enhanced detection efficacy with less false alarms relative to the utilization of all features. Wang et al. [13] proposed an anomaly-based intrusion detection system (IDS) utilizing the Online Sequential Extreme Learning Machine (OS-ELM) to tackle issues such as elevated data volume, diminished detection rates, and false positives. The method utilizes alpha profiling to decrease time complexity and a feature selection ensemble to eliminate unnecessary features, whereas beta profiling reduces the size of the training dataset. Farnaaz et al. [14] created an intrusion detection system utilizing a random forest classifier, capitalizing on

its enhanced efficacy compared to conventional techniques for attack classification. The model exhibited good detection accuracy and a low false alarm rate when evaluated on the NSL-KDD dataset, hence demonstrating its efficacy. This study evaluates all current machine learning approaches for IoT intrusion detection and presents the corresponding results.

III. METHODOLOGY

The concept of the Internet of Things (IoT) aims to expand the Internet's capabilities beyond traditional computers and smartphones to include a wide range of electronic and mechanical devices, sensors, and more. As the number of IoT applications grows, so too do the associated security vulnerabilities.

IoT devices are increasingly utilized in various sectors, including fire safety systems, drones, smart homes, and healthcare. The potential consequences of unauthorized access to these systems can be catastrophic. To mitigate these risks, organizations implement Network Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS), which monitor traffic for malicious activity and help safeguard their cloud, on-premise, or hybrid infrastructures.

A. Dataset

For this paper the UNSW-NB15 Dataset [15] was utilized. This dataset has been provided to us by UNSW Canberra. The dataset has collected nine sorts of attack scenarios, which comprises of Fuzzers, Analysis, Backdoors, Dos, Exploits, etc. are performed with the generated dataset. To preprocess and analyze this information, tools like Argus and Bro-IDS were used, enabling the extraction of 49 features via several methodologies.

B. Dataset Preparation

The dataset utilized in this study focuses on multi-class classification and comprises 81,173 rows and 69 columns. The target feature, `attack_cat`, represents the classification of network attacks into nine categories: *Analysis*, *Backdoor*, *DoS*, *Exploits*, *Fuzzers*, *Generic*, *Normal*, *Reconnaissance*, and *Worms*.

1) *Data Preprocessing*: To prepare the dataset for modeling, the following steps were undertaken:

- **Encoding Target Attribute:** The `attack_cat` attribute was encoded using `LabelEncoder()`, mapping each category to an integer label:
 - *Analysis* → 0,
 - *Backdoor* → 1,
 - *DoS* → 2,
 - *Exploits* → 3,
 - *Fuzzers* → 4,
 - *Generic* → 5,
 - *Normal* → 6,
 - *Reconnaissance* → 7,
 - *Worms* → 8.

The encoded labels were stored in the `label` attribute.

- **One-Hot Encoding:** The `attack_cat` attribute was also one-hot encoded to represent categories as binary vectors.

2) *Feature Selection*: After preprocessing, the dataset was reduced to 16 significant attributes, referred to as `multi_data`, for training and testing. These attributes are listed in the following tab: `filtered_features`

3) *Dataset Splitting*: The datasets were split into training and testing subsets as follows:

- The multi-class classification dataset (`multi_data`) was split with 70% of the data for training and 30% for testing.

4) *Target Feature*: The primary target feature for both datasets is `label`, which represents the encoded values of the `attack_cat` attribute.

C. Machine Learning Methods Used

1) *Decision Tree Classifier*: A decision tree classifier splits data into subsets based on feature values to form a tree structure. At each node, a decision is made to maximize information gain or minimize Gini impurity. [16], [17]

Information Gain (IG):

$$IG(S, F) = H(S) - \sum_{v \in \text{Values}(F)} \frac{|S_v|}{|S|} H(S_v), \quad (1)$$

where $H(S)$ is the entropy of the dataset S , and S_v represents subsets of S split by feature F .

Gini Impurity:

$$Gini = 1 - \sum_{j=1}^C p_j^2, \quad (2)$$

where p_j is class proportion of j instances in the dataset, and C is the total number of classes.

2) *K-Nearest-Neighbor Classifier*: The k -nearest neighbor (KNN) algorithm assigns a class label based on the majority class of the k nearest data points. [18], [19]

Distance Metric (Euclidean):

$$d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^d (u_i - v_i)^2}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} are data points in d -dimensional space.

The class label is determined by:

$$\hat{c} = \arg \max_{k \in C} \sum_{i \in N_k} \mathbb{I}(c_i = k), \quad (4)$$

where \mathbb{I} is the indicator function, N_k represents the k -nearest neighbors, and C is the set of classes.

3) *Linear Regression Model*: Linear regression is an ML model that returns the relationship model between a dependent variable y and independent variables X . [20], [21]

Model Equation:

$$y = w_0 + \sum_{j=1}^d w_j x_j + \epsilon, \quad (5)$$

where w_0 is the intercept, w_j are the coefficients, and ϵ is the error term.

Least Squares Objective:

$$\min_w \sum_{i=1}^n \left(y_i - w_0 - \sum_{j=1}^d w_j x_{ij} \right)^2, \quad (6)$$

where n is the number of data points.

4) *Linear Support Vector Machine (SVM)*: A linear SVM seeks to find the hyperplane that maximizes the margin between classes. [22]

Objective Function:

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}, b} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{w}\|^2 \quad \text{where } y_i(\mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{x}_i + b) \geq 1 \quad \forall i, \quad (7)$$

Here, \mathbf{w} is the weight, b is the bias, and y_i are the labels.

5) *Logistic Regression Model*: Logistic regression predicts probabilities using the sigmoid function. [23], [24]

Sigmoid Function:

$$P(y = 1 | \mathbf{x}) = \sigma(\mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{x} + b) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{x} + b)}}, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{w} is the weight vector, and b is the bias.

Log-Loss Function:

$$L(\mathbf{w}) = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i \log P(y_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - P(y_i))], \quad (9)$$

where n is the number of data points.

6) *Multi-Layer Perceptron Classifier (MLP)*: An MLP is a neural network with one or more hidden layers. It uses activation functions to model non-linearity. [25]

Feedforward:

$$\mathbf{z}^{(l+1)} = \mathbf{W}^{(l)} \mathbf{a}^{(l)} + \mathbf{b}^{(l)}, \quad \mathbf{a}^{(l+1)} = \phi(\mathbf{z}^{(l+1)}), \quad (10)$$

where ϕ is the activation function, $\mathbf{W}^{(l)}$ are weights, and $\mathbf{b}^{(l)}$ are biases.

Loss Function:

$$L = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^C y_{ik} \log \hat{y}_{ik}, \quad (11)$$

where \hat{y}_{ik} is the predicted probability for class k .

7) *Random Forest Classifier*: A random forest is an ensemble of decision trees trained on different subsets of the data and features. [14]

Prediction:

$$\hat{c} = \text{mode}(\{T_1(\mathbf{x}), T_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, T_K(\mathbf{x})\}), \quad (12)$$

where $T_k(\mathbf{x})$ is the prediction from the k -th tree.

IV. EXPERIMENTATION & RESULTS

A. Parameters of Accuracy

The performance of each model was evaluated using the following metrics:

- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE)**: The average magnitude of errors in predictions, calculated as:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (13)$$

where y_i are the true values, \hat{y}_i are the predicted values, and n is the total number of instances.

- **Mean Squared Error (MSE):** The average squared difference between predicted and actual values, defined as:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (14)$$

- **Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE):** The square root of MSE, given by:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{MSE} \quad (15)$$

- **R² Score:** The proportion of the variance in the dependent variable explained by the model, calculated as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (16)$$

where \bar{y} is the mean of the true values.

- **Accuracy:** The percentage of correctly classified instances, computed as:

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}} \times 100 \quad (17)$$

B. Experimental Results

Table II summarizes the performance of various models used for multi-class classification.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE METRICS OF MODELS

Model	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R ² Score	Accuracy (%)
Linear Regression	3.772	15.611	3.951	0.007	13.14
Logistic Regression	0.236	0.700	0.837	53.88	89.81
Linear SVM	0.235	0.699	0.836	53.99	89.89
KNN	0.265	0.808	0.899	46.73	88.55
Random Forest	0.256	0.782	0.885	47.83	89.06
Decision Tree	0.352	1.126	1.061	24.15	85.45
MLP	0.233	0.690	0.831	54.59	89.94

C. Prediction vs Real Values

Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the comparison of predicted vs actual values for Linear Regression and MLP models, respectively.

Fig. 1. Linear Regression: Predicted vs Real Values

Fig. 2. MLP: Predicted vs Real Values

D. Analysis of Results

The performance of each model indicates the following:

- **Linear Regression:** This model showed poor performance with low accuracy and high error values. The low R² score indicates that it does not explain the variability in the data effectively.
- **Logistic Regression and Linear SVM:** Both models performed well, with accuracies close to 90%. Their ability to model multi-class classification effectively stems from their robustness in handling linear decision boundaries.
- **KNN and Random Forest:** These models also performed well, with accuracies above 88%. However, their slightly higher error metrics suggest challenges in handling complex decision boundaries.
- **Decision Tree:** The model showed the lowest accuracy among tree-based methods, likely due to overfitting and a lack of regularization.
- **MLP:** The best-performing model with the highest accuracy (89.94%) and lowest error metrics. Its ability to learn complex, non-linear patterns makes it ideal for this task.

As shown in the results, MLP is the most effective model for this dataset, while Logistic Regression and Linear SVM are suitable alternatives due to their simplicity and competitive performance.

V. DEPLOYMENT AND MONITORING

A. Mobile Application for Real-Time Monitoring

To enable real-time prediction and monitoring, a React Native application was developed. This mobile application connects to a Flask server, which hosts the trained machine learning model. The app allows users to input relevant feature values and receive predictions instantly from the server. This setup ensures seamless integration between user interaction and model inference.

1) *Architecture Overview:* The deployment architecture consists of the following components:

- **React Native App:** A cross-platform mobile application that provides an intuitive interface for data entry and displays predictions. The app is designed to ensure ease of use and responsiveness.

- **Flask Server:** A lightweight Python-based web server that hosts the trained machine learning model. The server processes requests from the app, performs inference using the model, and returns predictions.
- **Model Inference:** The server loads the pre-trained machine learning model and uses the input features from the app to predict the output. The prediction is then sent back to the app.

2) *Workflow:* The system operates as follows:

- 1) The user inputs the required feature values into the app.
- 2) The app sends the input data to the Flask server via an HTTP POST request.
- 3) The server processes the request, loads the trained model, and performs inference on the input data.
- 4) The prediction result is sent back to the app in the form of an HTTP response.
- 5) The app displays the prediction result to the user.

3) *Technical Implementation:* The Flask server is implemented in Python and utilizes libraries such as `scikit-learn` to load the model. The key steps in the server-side implementation include:

- Loading the trained model at startup to minimize inference latency.
- Defining RESTful endpoints to handle requests from the mobile app.
- Performing input validation to ensure the integrity of the data received.

4) *Demo of the Application:* Figures 3 and 5 showcase the mobile app interface. Figure 3 illustrates the input screen, while Figure 5 displays the prediction result.

B. Mobile and Server algorithm

1) *Mobile algorithm:* The IoT Intrusion Detection Workflow outlines the process of detecting and handling intrusions in an IoT system. It begins by initializing necessary configurations, such as loading field labels and mandatory fields. The user can either choose a preset configuration or input custom data manually, with input validation ensuring that all mandatory fields are filled. In the case of missing optional data, randomization is applied to those fields. Once the data is ready, it is submitted to a server using a POST request, and the response is processed to extract the predicted results, including probabilities and labels. The results are displayed in a modal for user review, and the user is given options to toggle between raw and formatted outputs or to resend the request if necessary. This workflow provides a systematic approach to intrusion detection and user interaction with the system.

IoT Intrusion Detection (APP)

Input: Preset configuration values, Custom input values, Selected ML Model **Output:** Detection results with probabilities and classification label **Initialization:** Load field labels, mandatory fields, and preset configurations. **State Setup:** Initialize states for `isLoading`, `responseModalVisible`, `formData`, and selected

`preset/model`. **Preset Selection:** `preset` is selected `Populate formData` with preset values “Custom” is selected Allow manual user input for all fields **Input Validation:** each mandatory field field is empty Alert user: “Mandatory field is missing” **Randomization (if needed):** each empty optional field Assign randomized value **Data Submission:** Format `formData` into a single string for transmission Retrieve host and port from storage Send data to the server using POST request **Response Handling:** request succeeds Parse server response Extract probabilities and predicted label Display results in modal Show error alert **User Interaction:** Allow toggling between raw output and formatted results Provide options to close the modal or resend request

2) *Server algorithm:* The Prediction using Machine Learning Model algorithm focuses on making predictions based on data input and a selected machine learning model. It begins by parsing the incoming JSON data to extract the model name and input data. If either the model name or data is missing or invalid, an error message is returned. The algorithm proceeds by preprocessing the data, which includes converting categorical features to one-hot encoding, normalizing numerical data, and applying necessary transformations. After preparing the data, the algorithm loads the appropriate pre-trained model and makes predictions using the predict method, depending on the model’s capabilities. The final output includes the prediction results along with their associated probabilities. If any errors occur during the process, an error message is returned, ensuring that the model’s predictions are accurately processed and reported.

Prediction using ML Model (SERVER)

Input: JSON data containing `model_name` and `data`
Output: Prediction result with probabilities Parse the input JSON to extract `model_name` and `data`
`model_name` is missing or invalid Error: “Missing or Invalid model” `data` is missing Error: “Missing input data”
Preprocess the input data: Convert categorical columns to one-hot encoding Normalize numerical features using pre-trained scalers Apply necessary transformations based on the feature set Load pre-trained models from the stored model directory Select the model based on `model_name` from the loaded models Make predictions using the selected model: Model has `predict_proba` method Compute probabilities using `predict_proba` Compute predictions using `predict` Return the prediction and probabilities in JSON format **If any error occurs, return an error message with details.**

3) *Benefits of Deployment:* The integration of a React Native app with a Flask server provides several advantages:

- **Real-Time Prediction:** Enables users to quickly access predictions without the need for manual computation.
- **Cross-Platform Support:** The React Native app runs seamlessly on both iOS and Android devices.
- **Scalability:** The Flask server can be extended to handle

Fig. 3. Mobile App: Input Screen

Fig. 4. Mobile App: Model Selection Screen

Fig. 5. Mobile App: Model Prediction Screen

more complex models or additional functionalities.

- **User Accessibility:** The mobile app makes the solution more accessible to non-technical users.

VI. CONCLUSION

The work presented here has critically studied the efficiency of different machine learning models for NIDSs within IoT-enabled smart city networks using the UNSW-NB15 dataset in simulating realistic network traffic patterns. The results point out that machine learning algorithms like Decision Tree, K-Nearest Neighbor, Logistic Regression, and Random Forest classifiers have very bright prospects regarding detection and classification of network activity into normal and malicious activity classes. The comparison showed that all the models have their strengths, but Random Forest turned out to be an extremely robust classifier with very high accuracy rates and low false positive rates. This result points to the importance of choosing the right algorithms, considering specific characteristics of IoT traffic, which is often complex and heterogeneous. Besides, a new application for real-time network monitoring represents a practical development of IoT security. Integration of machine learning-based models into

this application can enable users to take a proactive approach toward security threats and provide safer environments for critical infrastructure sectors. However, certain algorithms are very computationally expensive, and the training usually requires a great deal of labeled data. Future research should try to overcome these limitations by finding lightweight models suitable for real-time applications and by developing strategies for efficient data labeling. This research, therefore, adds to the increasing knowledge base on IoT security with some insight into effective methodologies for intrusion detection. The findings of this study indicate that, with the increasing adoption of IoT devices across different industries, there is a need to ensure that proper security is in place to protect against cyber threats that are continuously evolving. Further research in this area will be required to further our understanding and improve the resilience of smart city networks against potential intrusions.

Future work in this area may be directed at the development of lightweight, efficient machine learning models intended for resource-constrained IoT devices. Since many IoT environments are computationally limited, algorithms that

achieve high accuracy with low latency and very low resource consumption must be considered. Hybrid models could be considered by researchers that use a mix of traditional machine learning with deep learning techniques; hence, it would allow detecting complex patterns in IoT network traffic without excessive computational overhead. The employment of federated learning approaches could allow the collaborative training of models in a distributed manner by IoT devices without compromising data privacy, further enhancing the applicability of NIDSs in real-world IoT networks.

Other potential future research directions include unsupervised or semi-supervised learning techniques to overcome the challenge of scarcity in labeled data. This allows intrusion detection systems to find anomalies and evolve with emerging threats without complete dependence on predefined datasets. Integrating contextual intelligence into NIDS can also be used to enhance their detection accuracy by considering specific device characteristics and behaviors within the IoT-enabled smart city networks. This may involve domain-specific ontologies or knowledge graphs to enable a better understanding of the device behavior pattern and interaction. It is such developments that are bound to help keep pace with the ever-increasing complexity of IoT environments and the dynamic nature of cyber threats.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Geyer and G. Carle, "Learning and generating distributed routing protocols using graph-based deep learning," in *Proceedings of the 2018 Workshop on Big Data Analytics and Machine Learning for Data Communication Networks*, pp. 40–45, 2018.
- [2] A. J. Moshayedi, A. S. Roy, H. Ghorbani, H. Lotfi, X. Zhang, L. Liao, and M. Gheisari, "A novel iot-enabled portable, secure automatic self-lecture attendance system: design, development and comparison," *International Journal of Electronic Security and Digital Forensics*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 663–689, 2024.
- [3] A. Shuvam Roy, H. Lan, M. Gheisari, a. AfzaalAbbasi, A. J. M. Moshayedi, L. liao, and S. M. Hosseini Bamakan, "Automation attendance systems approaches: A practical review," *BOHR International Journal of Internet of things, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning*, vol. 1, p. 25–34, Dec. 2022.
- [4] A. J. Moshayedi, A. S. Roy, L. Liao, A. S. Khan, A. Kolahdoz, and A. Eftekhari, "Design and development of foodiebot robot: From simulation to design," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 36148–36172, 2024.
- [5] A. S. Roy and A. Das, "Advanced path tracking and traffic management using ir sensors and timed automata," *Journal of Robotics Research (JRR)*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2024.
- [6] A. J. Moshayedi, A. Kolahdoz, A. S. Roy, S. A. L. Rostami, and X. Xie, "Design and promotion of cost-effective iot-based heart rate monitoring," in *International Conference on Cloud Computing, Internet of Things, and Computer Applications (CICA 2022)*, vol. 12303, pp. 405–410, SPIE, 2022.
- [7] A. Roy and P. Bagade, "Attentive-yolo: On-site water pipeline inspection using efficient channel attention and reduced elan-based yolov7," in *Proceedings of the 19th International Joint Conference on Computer Vision, Imaging and Computer Graphics Theory and Applications - Volume 4: VISAPP*, pp. 492–499, INSTICC, SciTePress, 2024.
- [8] D. G. Roy, B. Mahato, D. De, and R. Buyya, "Application-aware end-to-end delay and message loss estimation in internet of things (iot)—mqtt-sn protocols," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 89, pp. 300–316, 2018.
- [9] R. Kumar, M. Swarnkar, G. Singal, and N. Kumar, "Iot network traffic classification using machine learning algorithms: An experimental analysis," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 989–1008, 2021.
- [10] A. R. Gaidhani and A. D. Potgantwar, "A review of machine learning-based routing protocols for wireless sensor network lifetime," *Engineering Proceedings*, vol. 59, no. 1, p. 231, 2024.
- [11] M. E. Karsligl, A. G. Yavuz, M. A. Güvensan, K. Hanifi, and H. Bank, "Network intrusion detection using machine learning anomaly detection algorithms," in *2017 25th Signal Processing and Communications Applications Conference (SIU)*, pp. 1–4, 2017.
- [12] S. M. Hosseini Bamakan, H. Wang, T. Yingjie, and Y. Shi, "An effective intrusion detection framework based on mclp/svm optimized by time-varying chaos particle swarm optimization," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 199, pp. 90–102, 2016.
- [13] H. Wang, J. Gu, and S. Wang, "An effective intrusion detection framework based on svm with feature augmentation," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 136, pp. 130–139, 2017.
- [14] N. Farnaaz and M. Jabbar, "Random forest modeling for network intrusion detection system," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 89, pp. 213–217, 2016. Twelfth International Conference on Communication Networks, ICCN 2016, August 19– 21, 2016, Bangalore, India Twelfth International Conference on Data Mining and Warehousing, ICDMW 2016, August 19-21, 2016, Bangalore, India Twelfth International Conference on Image and Signal Processing, ICISP 2016, August 19-21, 2016, Bangalore, India.
- [15] N. Moustafa and J. Slay, "Unsw-nb15: a comprehensive data set for network intrusion detection systems (unsw-nb15 network data set)," in *2015 Military Communications and Information Systems Conference (MilCIS)*, pp. 1–6, 2015.
- [16] Y.-Y. Song and L. Ying, "Decision tree methods: applications for classification and prediction," *Shanghai archives of psychiatry*, vol. 27, no. 2, p. 130, 2015.
- [17] M. A. Ferrag, L. Maglaras, A. Ahmim, M. Derdour, and H. Janicke, "Rdtids: Rules and decision tree-based intrusion detection system for internet-of-things networks," *Future internet*, vol. 12, no. 3, p. 44, 2020.
- [18] R. Wazirali, "An improved intrusion detection system based on knn hyperparameter tuning and cross-validation," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 45, no. 12, pp. 10859–10873, 2020.
- [19] M. Mohy-Eddine, A. Guezzaz, S. Benkirane, and M. Azrou, "An efficient network intrusion detection model for iot security using knn classifier and feature selection," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 82, no. 15, pp. 23615–23633, 2023.
- [20] X. Su, X. Yan, and C.-L. Tsai, "Linear regression," *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Statistics*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 275–294, 2012.
- [21] M. A. Hamzah and S. H. Othman, "A review of support vector machine-based intrusion detection system for wireless sensor network with different kernel functions," *International Journal of Innovative Computing*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 59–67, 2021.
- [22] T. Joachims, "Training linear svms in linear time," in *Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*, pp. 217–226, 2006.
- [23] D. G. Kleinbaum, K. Dietz, M. Gail, M. Klein, and M. Klein, *Logistic regression*. Springer, 2002.
- [24] S. Chalichalamala, N. Govindan, and R. Kasarapu, "Logistic regression ensemble classifier for intrusion detection system in internet of things," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 23, p. 9583, 2023.
- [25] P. Shettar, A. V. Kachavimath, M. M. Mulla, G. Hanchinmani, et al., "Intrusion detection system using mlp and chaotic neural networks," in *2021 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI)*, pp. 1–4, IEEE, 2021.

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